

DETAILS OF FUNDS REQUESTEDMINIMUM BUDGET

AMOUNT REQUESTED: £ 1,200.

Transportation-

Insurance on Land Rover and motorbicycle.	£ 49
Land Rover-calculated on the distance of 35,000 kms. travelled in 1968-1969:	
Petrol.	£ 197
Oil	£ 25
Motorbicycle-petrol and oil for 2,000 kms.. . . .	£ 5
Maintenance and Repairs	<u>£ 200</u>
	£ 476

Research Expenses-

Pottery-transport and storage	£ 38
Photography	£ 65
Drafting.	£ 20
Recording	<u>£ 34</u>
	£ 157

Living Expenses-

For one year-October 1970 to September 1971 . . .	£ 550
Medical Insurance	£ 7
Medical Expenses.	<u>£ 10</u>
	<u>£ 567</u>
TOTAL	<u>£ 1,200</u>